

Movie Watching Preferences and Patterns: A Survey of the Female Students in the University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan

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Abstract

Movies are one of the media that are brilliant resources of leisure, records, and education for the people. human beings in every part of the world perceive movies as a form of amusement or a way to have amusing. these are critical media for the hundreds to be entertained via. human beings of every age, especially young people including girls are lots inquisitive about looking movies. in step with preceding research, women watch movies of genres like fantasy, journey, sci-fi, and many others. aside from romantic films, and now girls like to observe motion films. The purpose of this take a look at is to analyze the preferences and design of movie looking by using female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. A cross sectional observe become conducted to acquire statistics via making use of a purposive sampling method. The findings discovered that the female students watched movies of numerous genres; they in most cases watched movies on mobile. Similarly, it become observed that maximum of the female students watched movies just for amusement purposes.

Keywords: *Movie Watching Preferences, Sindh University Female Students, Watching styles.*

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Introduction

Films, also referred to as movies, are a kind of visible communicate that appoint moving photographs and sound to inform testimonies or train people some thing first rate. Those are some of the media that are extensive resources of leisure, data, and training for the masses (Baiju, 2019; Lehman & Luhr, 2018). Human beings perceive films as a kind of entertainment or a source to have a laugh. In line with SÁGVÁRI (2009), in modern-day societies, films and cinemas play a vital role for all generations, specially for the more youthful generation. While, Diefendorff and Chandler (2011) brought that movies go away their effect on humans with specific effect on character and precise behaviors (Ahmad, Shafi, & Shah, 2016). Moreover, Deáok (2008) attempted in his examine to discover the particular reasons that can be happy via looking movies.

Extraordinary movies have one of a kind affects on society. Comic, adventurous, biographical, and myth films provide a fine effect. Such films are just for leisure and make audience snicker and be satisfied. However, different forms of films like motion, mystery, and horror movies may additionally put a negative impact on society. Bearden and Etzel (1982) believed that inside the case of choosing manufacturers and products, organizations have identified their picks however within the case of films the impact of the picks of corporations want to be explored.

In step with Hofmeister-Tóth and Törőcsik (1996), film watching may be set down in each the visible and the invisible (or hidden) intake organizations. Client way of acting is considerably suffering from their on the spot environment. Zoltán and Lakatos (2011) put forth that movies have sizeable influences on minds, which in flip immediately relate to the mental behavior of people. While one isn't always capable of fulfil his wishes thru legal way, he could lodge closer to the loose resources or maybe illegal approach to download pirated movies for the fulfilment of his mental needs.

Modern-day technology, consisting of ladies, is a good deal inquisitive about watching films. Aside from romantic movies, Females watch genres like fantasy, journey, sci-fic and movement movies. These types of movies go away special affects on ladies, are in recent times very passionate about feminism-based movies like Sofia, brave, and many others. And because of these movies Females grow to be feminists, and due to the fable movies, many girls want to stay their existence like a princess.

Films additionally impact Females emotions and feelings. The general assumption in media production is that ladies and men revel in unique styles of films, and this may be supported via genre and content satisfaction (Gantz & Wenner, 1991). as an example, in a specific look at (Fischhoff, Antonio, & Lewis, 1998), it changed into proposed that "Womens movies" are films in which the story is

advised from the woman's factor of view (e.g., *Muriel's Wedding*), or wherein the story centres around girls and women's issues is commonly greater famous. The evaluation of literature discovered that there is a loss of research regarding film watching options and patterns in Pakistan. Consequently, the cause of this examine is to research the options and pattern of film looking by female students within the University of Sindh, Jamshoro.

Problem Statement

Movies are one of the critical mediums for the loads to be entertained via. people of all ages, mainly youth, watch movies with profound interest. According to Horváth, Gyenge, and Rácz (2015), numerous influences and resources of details affect the choices of university students concerning both the exercise of watching films and the selection of particular films. Maxfield (2003) said that there are remarkable family members amongst movie-viewing alternative and movie stars, trailers, issue remember, and genre.

Universities play an essential element in society, and university students pose a capacity target marketplace for film intake. Woman students of universities also watch films with unique patterns and options. In this manner, this observe objectives to evaluate what sort of films lady students within the University of Sindh, Jamshoro watch and what motivates them to pick out a film in their specific choice.

Furthermore, it's miles assumed that female students of college in the main watch films on cellular or laptops. Now and again in addition they watch films on television with the own family. Brought to this, there's also a fashion amongst them that each weekend females need to observe movies at the cinema. In addition, they choose to look at fable, drama, and romantic movies. While, a few share of them additionally pick to look at technological know-how fiction, horror, adventure, and motion movies. Ultimately, ladies in general watch movies just for entertainment.

Research Objectives

- To recognise the movie-watching choices among girl students in the UoS, Jamshoro
- To determine the movie looking styles among girl students in the UoS, Jamshoro

Research Questions

RQ1: What are movie-watching preferences among Female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro?

RQ2: What are the movie-watching patterns among Female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro?

Literature Review

This studies examines the movie looking patterns and choices of female students that how and what genres of films they watch commonly. A movie or movie is an photograph that creates an phantasm of transferring images at the display. Films also are a form of amusement. In recent times, movies are part of our society and way of life; film viewers have got so addicted that they cannot imagine their lives without looking films.

Furthermore, the term style is applied to any category of literature or other sort of enjoyment, e.g. track, either spoken, audio, or visible-primarily based movies etc. While, the primary purpose of each genre is to entertain the audiences in a one-of-a-kind fashion. In our society, as in many others while a brand new type comes, people forget about the old ones. There are one-of-a-kind genres of movies, e.g measures, revel in, farce, display, creativity, real, worry, romantic, science invention, and so forth. Various genres of movies have different influences on society. Some films are just for amusement and make viewers snigger and glad; whereas other movies like movement, mystery, and horror films, go away a bad effect on society. Bearden and Etzel (1982) believed that inside the case of selecting brands and products businesses have diagnosed their selections however within the case of movies, to know the influence of the companies need to be identified. Consistent with Hofmeister-Tóth and Törőcsik (1996), film watching may be put down in both the seen and the invisible (or hidden) consumption groups. And consumer behavior is notably stricken by their immediate environment, mainly the ones groups that one is, or would really like to be a member.

Zoltán and Lakatos (2011) write that movies have a widespread have an effect on on minds, which without delay relates to the mental behavior of people. One won't be capable of satisfy his desires via criminal approach. So, he would retreat towards the unfastened sources or perhaps illegal way to down load the pirated films for his mental wishes.

It can be referred to in some studies that human beings watch films with one-of-a-kind styles and alternatives. As some people watch movies at home with their own family, and some human beings watch films on the cinema with their pals. Human beings normally watch drama and comedy movies with their families. but, with pals, they watch all varieties of films. Within the early a long time, human beings in most cases watched movies on television, however now they have different method to observe on line on laptops and mobiles. In step with Hofmeister Toth (2006), the principle cause for this transformation in our society is human beings's behavior, suffering from their picks.

Moreover, it is familiar and natural that everyone has his likes and dislikes in the whole lot. Accordingly, everybody likes to observe specific genres of movies. Those those who are emotionally stable choose to observe movement, horror, and adventure movies. however, folks who are emotionally susceptible and tender-hearted decide upon to observe comedy, drama, and historical movies. Introduced within the context of movie watching purposes, a few human beings watch films just for entertainment; whereas, others watch films to benefit information. Consequently, the choice of various genres of movies to look at is likewise called the film-looking alternatives of humans.

Similarly, on this regard, Hirschman and Holbrook (1982) share that viewers selections and alternatives about the movie genres are evidently associated with their sensations and feelings or components of any revel in. Similarly, Zufryden (1996) also believed that the significance of genres or movie desire is diagnosed as the need and preferences of the humans.

Except, in a pilot look at, Horváth, Gyenge, and Rácz (2017) tested the movie viewing behavior of college students. It targeted at the diverse influences on assets of statistics, which impact their selection and picks. It concluded that viewers get facts about film awards on pirated webs and a few criminal film streaming services. Likewise, Horváth and Gyenge (2017), in a examine of movie viewing behavior of college and university students of Hungary concluded that for film choice, trailers are the main supply of facts for them. maximum students visit the film theatre with pals and big others.

Also, Chen, Gao, and Rau (2017) in a survey of 248 individuals regarding reasons for watching or not looking Danmaku motion pictures. The take a look at concluded that participants watched Danmaku films for facts, leisure, and social connectedness.

Research Method

On this quantitative take a look at, a pass-sectional survey approach changed into applied for statistics series. Concerning this, Wiseman and Aron (1970) defined a survey as a pretty based studies approach to obtain statistics from a huge number of respondents, who're presumed to be consultant of a particular population. Welman, Kruger, and Mitchell (2005) also aid that the survey approach lets in accumulating information from a larger pattern, as opposed to interviews or other kinds of facts gathering. The quantitative research of the study became conducted with the aid of questionnaires. The survey tool took between 5 to ten minutes to finish, contained most effective closed-ended questions, grouped into 5 sections, masking the respondents film viewing frequency, facts collecting techniques, movie viewing conduct, attitudes, and demographics. The sample consisted of female

students of Sindh University. SPSS software program device became used to analyze the information.

The populace of this have a look at was female students enrolled in Sindh University, Jamshoro. This University is one of the oldest universities in Pakistan. But, the centered respondents that are a complete of one hundred were purposively sampled from the following 5 departments. That is the Department of Media & Communication Studies, the Department of Psychology, the Branch of international family members, the Department of English and the Department of Arts & Design, 20 contributors every.

The statistics changed into gathered with the help of a pre-designed questionnaire. That had two main elements, one for demographic variables of the respondents. While, the opposite a part of the questionnaire consisted of such questions which aimed to searching for and collect opinions of the respondents about the movie looking patterns. Ultimately, the accumulated statistics were analyzed with descriptive information and were supplied in tables for description.

Analysis and Results

Demographic Information

Table 1: *Demographic characteristic (continued)*

Name of department		
Media and Communication Studies	20	(20.0)
Psychology	20	(20.0)
International Relations	20	(20.0)
English	20	(20.0)
Arts and Design	20	(20.0)
Total	100	(100)
Age		
18 to 22	82	(82.0)
23 to 27	17	(17.0)
28 and Above	1	(1.0)
Total	100	(100)
Mother Tongue		
Sindhi	30	(30.0)
Urdu	48	(48.0)

Punjabi	13	(13.0)
Balochi	2	(2.0)
Pashto	1	(1.0)
Saraiki	6	(6.0)
Total	100	(100)
Parent's Occupation		
Government Employee	53	(53.0)
Personal Business	26	(26.0)
Unemployed	2	(2.0)
Private Job	13	(13.0)
If other	6	(6.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 1 gives information approximately the demographic traits of the respondents who participated in this survey examine. On this way, it become located that the respondents who participated on this have a look at were enrolled in five diverse Institutes and Departments. This is the branch of Media & Communication Research (20.0%), the Department of Psychology (20.0%), the branch of worldwide members of the family (20.zero%), the Institute of English Language and Literature (20.0%), and the Institute of Arts and Design (20.0%) having the equal share of one 5th from every educational phase. 2d, situation to age corporations, it was observed that the majority share (82.0%) of the respondents become 18 to 22 years vintage. Delivered in the context of mom language, it changed into determined that the first highest share of about fifty percentage (48.0%) of the respondents stated that they spoke the Urdu language; whereas, the second one-maximum proportion of over than 1 / 4 (30.0%) spoke Sindhi; but, the remainder share (22.0%) spoke other various languages. Eventually, concerning mother and father occupation, the simple majority of the respondents (53.0%) said that their mother and father had a central authority process. The second-maximum percentage of over a quarter (26.0%) of the respondent's dad and mom had a personal business. Delivered the 0.33-maximum share of over one-tenth (13.0%) of the respondents cited that their dad and mom had a non-public job. While, the ultimate share of the respondents said their mother and father had other jobs (6.0%) and had been unemployed (2.0%).

Movie Watching Preferences

Table 2: *Movie Genre*

Movie Genre	Frequency	Percent
Action	2	(2.0)

Adventure	7	(7.0)
Horror	12	(12.0)
Romance	11	(11.0)
Fantasy	3	(3.0)
Science Fiction	2	(2.0)
Comedy	18	(18.0)
Thriller	10	(10.0)
Animated	1	(1.0)
Family	4	(4.0)
All	30	(30.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 2 has records about the alternatives of the respondents concerning the genre of movies they watched extra. In this way, it changed into seen that the percentage of over a quarter (30.0%) of the respondents mentioned that they watched films of all genres. but, in my opinion the primary highest share (18.0%) was folks who watched comedy films. Then in descending order have been the viewership of horror (12.0%), romance (11.0%), and thriller (10.0%) movies.

Table 3: *Movie Language*

Movie Language	Frequency	Percent (%)
English	42	(42.0)
Urdu	13	(51.0)
Tamil	1	(1.0)
Punjabi	4	(4.0)
If other	2	(2.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 3 presents statistics approximately the languages in which movies are watched greater by the respondents. As a result it become determined that the simple majority of them (51.0%) watched Urdu language movies. The second one-highest share of over -fifths (41.0%) of the respondents said that they watched English language movies. While the ultimate share of the respondents watched the movies of Tamil (1.0%), Punjabi (4.0%), and different languages (2.0%).

Table 4: *Movie Industry (continued)*

Industry	Frequency	Percent (%)
Hollywood	42	(42.0)

Bollywood	38	(38.0)
MOVIE WATCHING PREFERENCES AND PATTERNS		
Lollywood	17	(17.0)
Tollywood	1	(1.0)
If other	2	(2.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 4 has information about what industry movies are watched greater by way of the female students at the college of Sindh, Jamshoro. In this regard, it was visible that the primary highest share of over fifths (42.0%) of the respondents said that they watched films made by way of Hollywood. The second-maximum share of just about -fifths (38.0%) of the respondents expressed that they watched movies made by Bollywood. While, the third-highest percentage of nearly one-5th (17.0%) of the respondents stated that they watched films made through Lollywood. But, the final proportion of the respondents (3.0%) watched films made by using Tollywood (1.0%), and other (2.0%).

Movie Watching Patterns

Table 5: Sources to Seek Information about Movies

Movie Information Sources	Frequency	Percent (%)
Internet	50	(50.0)
Television	8	(8.0)
Magazine	1	(1.0)
YouTube	26	(26.0)
Friends	15	(15.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 5 affords information about the sources to get information regarding movies. As a result it changed into discovered that the first highest proportion of the size of 50 percentage (50.0%) of the respondents expressed that they were given information about movies from the net. Added for the second one-highest percentage of a touch over a quarter (26.0%) of the respondents, the supply for receiving statistics concerning movies was YouTube. Whereas, the 1/3-maximum share of over one-10th (15.0%) of the respondents noted that they got information approximately films from their buddies. However, for the remaining share (9.0%),

the source for getting facts approximately films become television (8.0%) and magazines (1.0%).

Table 6: *Movie Watching Device (continued)*

Device	Frequency	Percent (%)
Television	12	(12.0
Laptop	41	(41.0
Mobile	43	(43.0
DVD	1	(1.0
Tab	1	(1.0
MOVIE WATCHING PREFERENCES AND PATTERNS 65		
If other	2	(2.0
Total	100	(100)

Table 6 gives statistics about what devices are used for looking movies by way of the female students within the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. On this regard, it become assessed that the primary highest proportion of over -fifths (43.0%) of the respondents noted that they watched films on cell. Whereas, the second-maximum percentage, sizing better than -fifths (41.0%) said that they watched movies at the pc. Introduced the 1/3-highest share of over one-10th (12.0%) of the respondents instructed that they watched films on tv. Ultimately, the closing share (4.0%) of the respondents expressed that they used DVD (1.0%), Tab (1.0%), and different devices (2.0%).

Table 7: *Movie Watching Place*

Place	Frequency	Percent (%)
Cinema	26	(26.0)
Home	67	(67.0)
Friend's home	2	(2.0)
Hostel	5	(5.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 7 provides information approximately the place in which the respondents watched movies. In this way, it changed into discovered that the first highest proportion of over then three-fifths (67.0%) of the respondents said that they watched films at domestic. The second one-highest percentage of the scale of a touch higher than a quarter (26.0%) of the respondents cited that they would go to view

movies within the cinema. Whereas, the last percentage of (7.0%) of the respondents said that they watched movies on the hostel (5.0%) and a buddies domestic (2.0%).

Table 8: *Cinema Visits Monthly*

Visits Monthly	Frequency	Percent (%)
One	12	(47.0)
Twice	9	(35.0)
Thrice	5	(18.0)
Total	26	(100)

Table 8 has statistics concerning the ones respondents who watched movies in cinemas. Consequently it was similarly recognised about the frequency of their cinema visits that the primary highest proportion of approximately fifty percentage (47.0%) of these respondents who watched movies in cinemas informed that they visited cinema as soon as a month. The second-maximum share of better than one-third (35.0%) of the respondents cited that they visited the cinema twice a month. However, the last percentage of virtually one-5th (18.0%) stated that they visited the cinema three times a month.

Table 9: *Social Context of Movie Watching*

Watching with	Frequency	Percent (%)
Family	20	(20.0)
Friends	24	(24.0)
Alone	56	(56.0)
Partner	6	(6.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 9 gives information approximately the social situation surrounding the respondents while looking films via them. Thus on this regard, it changed into visible that the proportion sizing higher than fifty percent (56.0%) of the respondents said that they watched movies whilst being on my own. The second-maximum proportion of just about 1 / 4 (24.0%) expressed that they watched movies with friends; whereas, the last share, sizing one-fifth (20.0%) of the respondents, stated that they watched films with their circle of relatives.

Table 10: *Purpose of Watching Movie*

Purpose	Frequency	Percent (%)
Information	6	(6.0)
Entertainment	73	(73.0)
Time pass	21	(21.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 10 has statistics regarding the motive of the film-looking with the aid of the female students within the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. Consequently the information stated that the primary maximum percentage of almost three quarters (73.0%) of the respondents said that they watched movies for amusement. The second one-highest proportion of over one-fifth (21.0%) said that they watched films for time skip. Whereas, the closing percentage sizing just (6.0%) of the respondents expressed that their intention to look at films turned into to get information.

Table 11: *Watching Number of Movies Weekly*

Number of Movies	Frequency	Percent (%)
One	65	(65.0)
Two	17	(17.0)
Three	11	(11.0)
More than 3	7	(7.0)
Total	100	(100)

Table 11 gives records approximately the quantity of movies watched in per week by using female students inside the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. On this manner, it turned into discovered that the primary maximum proportion of over 3-fifths (65.0%) of the respondents stated that they watched one film in a week. The second one-highest percentage of the respondents sizing a little much less than one-fifth (17.0%) stated that they watched two movies in a week. Delivered the third-highest percentage of better than one-tenth (11.0%) of the respondents expressed that they watched three movies in a week. But, the closing share sizing simply much less than one-tenth (7.0%) of the respondents discovered that they watched more than three films in a week.

Discussion and Conclusion

The motive of this have a look at changed into to assess and decide the movie-looking options and patterns of the female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. On this manner, it became found first approximately their demographic

traits of the surveyed female students belonging to five diverse departments and institutes of the University of Sindh, Jamshoro, and age-sensible; the significant majority of them have been 18 to 22 years vintage. Further, the majority of them stated that they spoke Urdu and Sindhi language. Eventually, the easy majority of the survey contributors shared that their dad and mom were authorities employees.

Regarding film watching options first about their preference of the genre of movies, it was found that the best share that is over 1 / 4 (30.0%) of them, cited that they watched the movies of all genres. Then for my part, the 3 maximum famous film genres many of the female students at the University of Sindh, Jamshoro, were in descending order comedy, horror, and romance. Whereas difficulty to the language of the films, it become observed that the respondents watched broadly speaking the films first in Urdu language and then the English language. However, inside the context of the global movie enterprise, it become visible that they ordinarily watched films made by early Hollywood after which Bollywood.

1/3, within the context of film watching patterns, it became located that the three most favorite assets of looking for data approximately movies most of the female students inside the University of Sindh, Jamshoro were in descending order: net, YouTube, and pals. added to that, the female students also said that the two most used devices among them to observe films have been mobile telephones and laptops. As far as the area and social context for looking films were worried, then the girl college students said that the full-size majority of them watched films at home, after which a proportion of a quarter of them watched films at the cinema. But, most people of the female students expressed that they preferred to look at movies on my own; just a sector of them watched films with friends or family. Delivered folks who watched movies in cinemas among them almost fifty percentage expressed that their frequency of touring cinemas was just once in a month. Eventually, most of the people of the female students said that their primary reason to observe films is to seek entertainment in preference to statistics or time bypass. However, their frequency of looking movies become located to be one film in a week.

Limitations of the study

The statistics for this have a look at became accumulated from the a hundred female students by using purposely decided on five Departments of the Faculty of Social Sciences and Arts of the University of Sindh, Jamshoro. as a consequence the consequences aren't so generalizable.

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